

“TIKTOK” METHOD: EXPLICIT INSTRUCTIONS IN IMPROVING THE READING COMPREHENSION OF GRADE 11 HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Reading is an important skill that must be developed by the students to prepare themselves in facing the competitive world of work. With that being said, Carrascal National High School conducted a Group Screening Test (GST) to determine students who need more guidance and supervision in reading. The identified “frustration” readers were subjected to a One-on-One Reading Activity to ascertain the common reason of their status. Based on the result, poor vocabulary has been on top which delivered the researcher the fervor to develop an intervention to improve reading comprehension. The present action research investigated the effectiveness of “TIKTOK” method (*Think, Integrate, Know, Transcribe, Optimize, Knit*) in improving the reading comprehension of the subjects focusing on their vocabularies. Student participants (n=7) were the identified “frustration” readers in Grade 11 HUMSS Makatao and MakaDiyos who were subjected to an intervention. The research yielded a positive result of producing “instructional” readers both in GST and One-on-One Reading Activity with a mean score of 9 in GST with a comprehension level of “instructional” and a mean percentage score of 60 in One-on-One Reading with a comprehension level of “instructional” based on the scaling specified in Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI) Manual. Reading materials were adopted from the Phil-IRI for quality assurance. Finally, one student was still classified as “frustration” reader even after the implementation of the intervention which implied that the use of “TIKTOK” method for some students required a series of cycle before concluding its efficacy due to unique learning habits, style and multiple intelligences.

Keywords: *Reading, TIKTOK Method, Phil-IRI*

INTRODUCTION

Macro skills in communication are the most important skills in teaching a particular language. Each of them is indispensable in the learning process and teaching performance on behalf of the learners and mentors. These skills such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing will use as the main vehicle to obtain definitely a certain language and to serve as a conduit to encompass widely the interrelated realms of communication and global community (Macro Skills Teaching, n.d).

Reading as one of the macro skills in learning a language is defined as a cognitive process that involves decoding symbols to arrive at meaning. It is an active process of constructing meanings of words. Reading with a purpose helps the reader to direct information towards a goal and focuses their attention. Although the reasons for reading may vary, the primary purpose of reading is to understand the text (Sandhu, 2022).

However, reading is one of the common concerns of the teachers that is not totally developed among the learners. In the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), the Philippines scored lowest in Reading out of 79 countries. The PISA further showed that only one in five Filipino learners aged 15 achieved at least the minimum proficiency level in Overall Reading Literacy (San Juan, 2019). This number produced a loud uproar in the Department of Education thrusting the senate to pass a bill to address the problem. In fact, Gatchalian's Senate Bill 150 or the Academic Recovery and Accessible Learning (ARAL) Act seeks to institute a nationwide learning recovery program that will include well-systematized tutorial sessions and well-designed remediation plans. He also proposed to officially make every November National Reading Month under Senate Bill 475, to be celebrated with nationwide reading programs and activities and inculcate a culture of reading among basic education learners and their communities (Philippine News Agency, 2022).

As a result, the Department of Education disseminated to all public elementary and secondary schools DepEd Memo No. 173 s. 2019 the need to strengthen the reading proficiency of every learner and to nurture a culture of reading which is a requisite skill in all content areas. This mandated the teachers to inject reading activities to the learners during their class periods to intensify the commitment to make every learner a reader at his/her grade level.

Nonetheless, looking at the grassroots of education, there are still students who encountered challenges in reading particularly in the word recognition and comprehension. According to Perfetti (n.d), difficulties with fluent word reading can stem from different underlying causes. Problems with automatic word recognition can contribute to difficulties with fluency, and in turn, often cause problems with comprehension. Fluent reading is necessary for comprehension, because attention required for effortful reading draws resources away from comprehension.

Considering that there are many factors affecting the reading skills of the students, teachers have the capability to strategize varied interventions to support and to cater the

needs of the learners. Hence, teachers must design methods or interventions that will serve as a scaffold in improving students' performance. Bidabadi et. al. (2016) illustrated that a good teaching method helps the students to question their preconceptions, and motivates them to learn, by putting them in a situation in which they come to see themselves as the authors of answers, and as the agents of responsibility for change.

As directed by the Department of Education to conduct reading examinations in all grade levels to determine the comprehension skills of the students, Carrascal National High School was serious in implementing the mandate. As a result, there were few students in Grade 11 HumSS Strand who were classified as "frustration" readers. To define exactly the root cause of such event, a one-on-one reading text was conducted. Based on the feedback of the subjects, they have difficulty understanding the text due to poor vocabulary that greatly affected their reading comprehension. Hence, "TIKTOK" method was constructed.

Finally, the conduct of this "TIKTOK" method will serve as an intervention vehicle for the teachers in improving the reading skills chiefly of the 7 Grade 11 HumSS students belonging to sections Makatao and MakaDiyos of Carrascal National High School who were identified with "frustration" level in the mentioned macro skill. They have difficulties in comprehending the material due to poor vocabularies. Accordingly, this method is purposely made to create a more authentic learning while promoting meaningful and enjoyable experience. Also, this method will capture not only what the students know about the reading skill but likewise to apply that knowledge in a "real- world" situation. Combining both the integrated approach and performance- based assessment will definitely contribute to the students' acquisition of the 21st century skills while improving their academic performance.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of utilizing 'TIKTOK' Method in improving the reading comprehension level of the Grade 11 HUMSS students. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the student's comprehension level in GST and one-on-one reading before implementing an intervention?
2. What is the student's comprehension level in GST and one-on-one reading after implementing an intervention?
3. Is there a significant difference between the comprehension level of the students' GST and one-on-one reading scores before and after the implementation of the intervention?

METHODOLOGY

The researcher utilized a "TIKTOK" method as an intervention to improve reading comprehension of the subjects focusing on their vocabulary development. "TIKTOK" stands for **Think, Integrate, Know, Transcribe, Optimize, Knit**. It is a method that is

designed to tailor fit the needs of the students. It will allow the teacher to structure an entire instruction that will serve as a scaffold in mastering the reading skill.

Think is the first stage where the teacher identifies the possible reason why the learner failed to reach independent and instructional reading level. According to Nathan V, there mainly causes for problems in reading comprehension.

A. Decoding Difficulties

1. Trouble sounding out words and recognizing words out of context;
2. Confusion between letters the sounds they present;
3. Slow oral reading rate (reading word by word)
4. Reading without expressions;
5. Ignoring punctuation while reading

B. Comprehension Difficulties

1. Confusion about the meaning of words and sentences;
2. Inability to connect ideas in a passage;
3. Omission of, or glossing over details;
4. Difficulty distinguishing significant information from minor details;
5. Lack of concentration during reading.

C. Retention Difficulties

1. Trouble remembering or summarizing what is read;
2. Difficulty connecting what is read to prior knowledge;
3. Difficulty applying content of a text to personal experiences.

In this case, the identified difficulty encountered by the respondents was the reading comprehension. According to the learners, they have the tendency to misunderstand the selection because they were not capable of pulling out main points and absorbing more information due to lack of vocabularies. As a result, they cannot provide the exact answer to the follow-up questions.

Once the reason is clear, **Integrate** will follow. The teacher will start utilizing a technique that will serve as a strategy in teaching the student what to do in mastering the macro skill. Since the problem has been defined, the researcher will commence the use of “ENGLISH” to help the students improve their reading comprehension level. While giving the students enough time to read a given selection, they will start using the “ENGLISH” technique.

E- Elicit unknown words from the story that are difficult to decode.

N- Navigate the meaning of the words from the dictionary (printed or online).

G- Generate synonyms and antonyms of the unknown words.

L- Learn to demonstrate each unknown words by acting it out in front of the teacher.

I- Illustrate understanding of words by crafting tailored sentences.

S- Scamper to the part of the story where the unknown word was used.

H- Have the student discuss the story based on their understanding.

Know is the third phase where the teacher provides written questions to be answered by the students to determine their reading comprehension level.

The fourth phase is **Transcribe**. It is significant to necessitate the students to write the important details they have assimilated from the discussion of the teacher to determine their level of understanding. This stage will end by tasking the learners to compose their personal reflections and make a summary about their learning.

S	State the importance of vocabulary in reading comprehension.
I	Identify the unknown words.
N	Note personal sentences using the unknown words.
T	Think of other challenges you encountered in reading the selection/story.
O	Offer solutions to overcome the identified challenges.
S	Summarize your learning.

Optimize takes the fifth stage where the students will be given with different reading materials with follow-up questions to practice his/her reading comprehension. This is a long-term activity where teacher required the students to continue reading as part of the continuous learning. When students continue to struggle with the language, most of the time we would tell them to spend more time practicing the language skills. Thus, reading more materials can optimize their comprehension skills.

The final phase is **Knit**. This is where the students will join together the concepts, knowledge, and ideas attained from the intervention.

The researcher-made “TIKTOK” method is the combination of various strategies present in each part of the method. It addresses the different needs of the students thus, making it useful to the teachers. The promptness of this research is due to the specific reason of having poor vocabulary affecting students’ reading comprehension making them as “frustrated” readers. Digging inspiration from the present scenario, the utilization of “TIKTOK” Method in mastering reading comprehension skill has been established.

The intervention will be carried out during the first quarter of second semester of school year 2022-2023 in Grade 11 Humss students in Carrascal National High School.

Action Research Method

A. Participants and/or Other Sources of Data and Information

This study was conducted in Carrascal National High School located at National Highway, Barangay Gamuton, Carascal, Surigao del Sur. Specifically, the study was piloted in the Senior High School Department employing Grade 11 HUMSS students of sections Makatao and MakaDiyos. Specifically, there were 3 students from Makatao and 4 students in MakaDiyos.

This study employed a reading material as the primary source of data. The materials were adapted from the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) to ensure quality assurance.

The simulation of the intervention happened on March 31, 2023, Friday during ICL period with the Grade 11 STEM students to test the efficacy of the method. The intervention was officially conducted on April 17- May 3, 2023 comprising the 9th and 10th week of the 3rd quarter during the review weeks before the final examination to avoid disruption of regular classes of the subjects.

B. Data Gathering Methods

On January 2023, the researcher conducted a “Group Screening Test” (GST) to determine the reading capabilities of the grade 11 students. A 20- item test was administered and scores were interpreted. After the test, 10 HumSS students who scored 1-7 were classified as “frustration” and subjected to one-on-one reading activity. During the one-on-one activity on February 2023, 3 out of 5 students in grade 11 HumSS Makatao and 4 out of 5 learners in MakaDiyos were still classified as “frustration” readers since they got below 58% in their comprehension score or the students failed to get 3 correct answers out of 5 questions.

The reading material from the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) was adapted to identify the decoding difficulties of the students including but not limited to sounding of words, punctuation marks, confusion between letters and slow oral reading as well as retention difficulties and comprehension difficulties. The result of the activity determined students who were considered as “frustrated” readers and they were subjected to an intervention.

During the intervention on April 2023, the researcher administered the “TIKTOK” Method following the logical order of steps to make sure that students’ needs were addressed. The method aimed to improve the reading comprehension of the students from “frustration level” to “instructional” and “independent” readers.

After the intervention, different reading material was given to the students for the post-reading to identify the efficacy of the “TIKTOK” Method and to prevent discrepancies on the result since some of the learners have the tendency to memorize or remember the correct answers of the previous material. The reading material was adopted from the PHIL-IRI to ensure the same level of difficulty as to the material used during the pre-reading activity. Also, another 20- item test for GST was administered to determine if there was an improvement in the students’ reading comprehension. Comparison and interpretation of result happened after the collection of data.

While the learner was reading a selection, an assessment tool was used by the researcher to decide the comprehension score attained by the students. The instrument was taken from the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) to maintain quality

assurance. A letter of consent was submitted to the office of the principal to have a permission to conduct the action research.

Finally, the data gathered from the actual implementation of intervention was analyzed and interpreted using the percentage of correct answers to comprehension questions as specified in the Phil-IRI Manual page 21.

Table 1: Table of Percentage for Comprehension Scores (One-on-One)

No. of Items	Score in Comprehension	%
5	5	100
	4	80
	3	60
	2	40
	1	20

Table 2: Phil-IRI Oral Reading Profile (One-on-One)

Reading Level	Comprehension Score (in %)
Independent	80-100
Instructional	59-79
Frustration	58% and below

Table 3: Group Screening Test (GST) Level

Reading Levels & Scores			
14 & Above	8 to 13	1 to 7	0
(Independent)	(Instructional)	(Frustration)	Non-Reader

RESULTS

1. What is the student's comprehension level in GST and one-on-one reading before implementing an intervention?

Table 4. GST and One-on-One Comprehension Level Before Intervention

Student	Group Screening Test (GST) Scores		One-on-One Reading Scores		
	Before	Comprehension Level	Before	%	Comprehension Level
1	6	Frustration	2	40	Frustration
2	5	Frustration	2	40	Frustration
3	6	Frustration	2	40	Frustration
4	4	Frustration	1	20	Frustration
5	6	Frustration	2	40	Frustration
6	5	Frustration	2	40	Frustration
7	5	Frustration	1	20	Frustration
Mean	5.3	Frustration	1.7	34	Frustration

GST: 20- item test; One-on-one reading: 5-item comprehension questions

Table 4 presented the reading performances of the subjects before the implementation of the “TIKTOK” method both in GST and one-on-one reading. All of the students were identified as “frustration” readers based on the scores they attained as defined in Phil-IRI Manual with a total GST mean score of 5.3 with a comprehension level of “frustration” and One-on-One Reading percentage score of 34 with a comprehension level of “frustration.” The scores signified that the learners failed to comprehend the given materials because of their poor vocabulary. According to the study of Nanda and Azmy (2020), they indicated that poor reading comprehension occurs due to three remarkable factors which were students; lack of motivation, low prior knowledge and poor English vocabulary. Having limited vocabulary has been identified as an impairment of reading comprehension and thus, the government emphasized that students must master between 2,500 to 3, 000 English words to comprehend English academic texts.

Lastly, this result served as an eye-opener most particularly to the educators to look for solutions to address the problem in reading comprehension. Developing interventions must be seriously shaped and constructed to help the learners acquire the needed skill to face the competitive world of work.

2. What is the student’s comprehension level in GST and one-on-one reading after implementing an intervention?

Table 5. GST and One-on-One Comprehension Level After Intervention

Student	Group Screening Test (GST) Scores		One-on-One Reading Scores		
	After	Comprehension Level	Afetr	%	Comprehension Level
1	9	Instructional	3	60	Instructional
2	9	Instructional	2	40	Frustration
3	8	Instructional	3	60	Instructional
4	12	Instructional	4	80	Independent
5	11	Instructional	3	60	Instructional
6	8	Instructional	3	60	Instructional
7	9	Instructional	3	60	Instructional
Mean	9	Instructional	3	60	Instructional

GST: 20- item test; One-on-one reading: 5-item comprehension questions

The table showed the significant progress made by the respondents in GST and One-on-One Reading activities after the implementation of the “TIKTOK” method. In Group Screening Test (GST), all of the subjects got a number of correct answers ranging from 8-13 making them an “instructional” reader with a mean GST score of 9.

In one-on-one reading test, 6 students out of 7 were classified as “instructional” and “independent” readers respectively based on the classification of scores defined in Phil-IRI Manual. Majority of them got 3 correct answers out of 5 comprehension questions and 1 got 4 correct answers. However, one student was still considered as “frustration” reader since she got only 2 correct answers even after the used of the method.

The result signified that the intervention utilized by the researcher failed to produce 100% instructional and independent readers. Nonetheless, the improvement in the reading comprehension has denoted the effectiveness of the “TIKTOK” method in enhancing the vocabulary of the learners leading to better reading comprehension. In the study piloted by Wanzek et al. (2017), they examined the multicomponent reading intervention for students with reading comprehension difficulties including the latent word reading, and latent vocabulary. Their findings indicated that students receiving the intervention made greater gains in reading comprehension than students who did not receive the intervention. This implied that the implementation of intervention played a major role in developing and enhancing the academic performance and skills of the students. Hence, teachers should develop strategic materials and methods to aid the learners in acquiring the expected skills that they can use in the future.

3. Is there a significant difference between the comprehension level of the students’ GST and one-on-one reading scores before and after the implementation of the intervention?

Table 6. GST and One-on-One Comprehension Level Before and After Intervention

STUDENT	Group Screening Test (GST) Scores				One-on-One Reading Scores					
	Before	Comprehension Level	After	Comprehension Level	Before	%	Comprehension Level	After	%	Comprehension Level
1	6	Frustration	9	Instructional	2	40	Frustration	3	60	Instructional
2	5	Frustration	9	Instructional	2	40	Frustration	2	40	Frustration
3	6	Frustration	8	Instructional	2	40	Frustration	3	60	Instructional
4	4	Frustration	12	Instructional	1	20	Frustration	4	80	Independent
5	6	Frustration	11	Instructional	2	40	Frustration	3	60	Instructional
6	5	Frustration	8	Instructional	2	40	Frustration	3	60	Instructional

7	5	Frustration	9	Instructional	1	20	Frustration	3	60	Instructional
MEAN	5.3	Frustration	9	Instructional	1.7	34.3	Frustration	3	60	Instructional

GST: 20- item test; One-on-one reading: 5-item comprehension questions

The table summarized the comprehension level of the students in GST and one-on-one reading before and after the intervention. It clearly showed the significant improvement in the reading comprehension of the subjects after the implementation of the “TIKTOK” method. The total GST mean score of the students before the method was 5.3 with a comprehension level of “frustration” as defined by the Phil-IRI manual. After the intervention, the total mean GST score was 9 with a comprehension level of “instructional.”

Furthermore, the total percentage score of the respondents in one-on-one reading was 34.3 with a comprehension level of “frustration.” However, after the intervention the performance of the students was improved with a total percentage score of 60 with a comprehension level of “instructional.”

Hence, the researcher was successful in improving the reading comprehension skills of the students by enriching their vocabularies through explicit instructions using the “TIKTOK” method. This claim was supported by the study conducted by Nilsson (2021), when she clearly stated that targeted reading instruction intervention supported growth in vocabulary development, comprehension, and phonological awareness of the students. With the data presented, it encouraged the teachers to craft various interventions to improve the reading comprehension of the students.

Group Screening Test (p<0.05)

Paired Samples T-Test

			statistic	df	p
A	B	Student's t	-5.62	6.00	0.001

One-on-One Reading (p<0.05)

Paired Samples T-Test

			statistic	df	p
A	B	Student's t	-3.58	6.00	0.012

Based on the result of the paired t-test, both GST and One-on-One Reading yielded a p-value of 0.001 and 0.012 respectively which were less than the significant value of 0.05. This signified that the implementation of the “TIKTOK” method produced a statistically significant results that indicated strong evidence against the null hypothesis.

Hence, accept the alternative hypothesis that there is a significant difference between the comprehension level of the students’ GST and one-on-one reading scores before and after the implementation of the intervention.

Conclusions

- The comprehension level of the students in GST and one-on-one reading before and after the intervention clearly showed the significant improvement in the reading comprehension of the learners after the implementation of the “TIKTOK” method. The total GST mean score of the students before the method was 5.3 with a comprehension level of “frustration” as defined by the Phil-IRI manual. After the intervention, the total mean GST score was 9 with a comprehension level of “instructional.”
- Furthermore, the total percentage score of the respondents in one-on-one reading activity before the intervention was 34.3 with a comprehension level of “frustration.” However, after the intervention the performance of the students was improved with a total percentage score of 60 with a comprehension level of “instructional.”
- Hence, the researcher was successful in improving the reading comprehension skills of the students by enriching their vocabularies through explicit instructions using the “TIKTOK” method. This claim was supported by the study conducted by Nilsson (2021), when she clearly stated that targeted reading instruction intervention supported growth in vocabulary development, comprehension, and phonological awareness of the students. With the data presented, it encouraged the teachers to craft various interventions to improve the reading comprehension of the students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author sought an approval from the Office of the Principal of Carrascal National High School to conduct the action research to the Grade11 Humanities and Social Sciences (HumSS) students. Respondents were well-informed on the purpose and objectives of the research and they have the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time as they wanted to. Parents’ consent was also provided to inform the parents on the conduct of the research and that their children were considered as the respondents.

Respondents’ identity were kept confidential at all times to safeguard the well-being of the students. The author also declared that there has no conflict of interest while doing the action research.

The author also attested to the originality of the research and has cited properly all the references used. Finally, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and the results were utilized purely for research.

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